

Sensor-level Magnetoencephalography (MEG) Analysis of Auditory Processing in Children

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Abstract

Hearing impairments are prevalent in children, often leading to significant challenges in cognitive and social development. Magnetoencephalography (MEG) is an advanced neuroimaging modality that offers accurate assessment of brain activity, rendering it essential for investigating auditory processing abnormalities. This study aimed to identify significant MEG channels that differentiate children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) from typically developing (TD) children during auditory processing tasks. By analyzing MEG data from both gradiometer and magnetometer channels developed a channel significant index that facilitates the identification of relative better significant channel for differentiate ASD related hearing impairments. Our results indicate that the gradiometers were more sensitive than magnetometers thus confirming their potential use in investigating the cortex.

Key words: hearing impairments, autism spectrum disorders, Magnetoencephalography, Gradiometers, Magnetometers

Introduction

The hearing impairments are wide range of conditions that affect ability to perceive, process or interpret speech and sounds. This extends to central dysfunctions of the auditory processing pathways of the brain, and peripheral damage of sensorineural hearing loss [1]. Those are also common in people with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), which impair communication, interaction with others, and academic performance. Children with ASD frequently encounter difficulties in understanding speech and other auditory inputs, impeding their capacity to react to contextual cues [2]. This may affect their ability to learn and interact with others. There is a desperate need to act efficiently and promptly in case of auditory processing anomalies to prevent the decline in the language growth, social skills and overall quality of living [3]. It is the complexity of the disorder and the various manifestations of the disorder in a number of individuals that make it hard to detect auditory processing disorders in children with ASD. Traditional behavioral tests may fail to identify finer auditory processing impairments, which is why the need to integrate more advanced, objective measures of diagnosis.

MEG provides unique non-invasive methods for recording fast neural oscillation in a large number of channels. Its high temporal and spatial resolution that allows a precise tracking of brain activity in response to auditory stimuli [4,5]. MEG captures the magnetic field generated by neural activity, facilitating the understanding of the timing and location of the brain activity. MEG is an excellent method for examining how Children with ASD interpret auditory stimuli, as it enables researchers to analyze brain activity at the sensor level with remarkable precision [6-8].

This work demonstrates large scale brain differences related to auditory processing in children with ASD vs controls with traditional developing (TD) children. We contrast the gradiometer and magnetometer channel recordings to see how this neural activity differs for the two groups. The aim of the study will be to generate a neural index that provides the means to differentiate between individuals with ASD and TD based upon their auditory processing profile. An early marker of a presumably auditory processing disorder, shown by a neural index can be useful when establishing an early diagnosis and possibly finding the right intervention.

Methods

Results and Discussion

Table 1 summarizes the distribution of channels across the four tiers, along with their effect sizes (Cohen’s d) and p-values.

Tier	Number of channels	GRAD/MAG	Sample channel	Sample p-value	Sample cohen’s d
Tier 1(Strong)	05	Gradiometers 04 Magnetometers 01	MEG0133	0.045	0.56
Tier 2(Moderate)	22	Gradiometers 20 Magnetometers 02	MEG0111	0.056	0.466
Tier 3(Weak)	41	Gradiometers 31 Magnetometers 10	MEG0222	0.109	0.373
Tier 4(Non)	238	Gradiometers 149 Magnetometers 89	MEG2443	0.824	0.052

Table 1: Channel Tiering with Sample Statistics.

The gradiometer channels were found to be more sensitive to the differences in auditory-processing difference between TD and ASD individuals. Statistical analysis using independent t-tests revealed that several gradiometer channels exhibited significant differences in variance between the groups. Effect Sizes: For the gradiometer channels, Cohen’s d values ranged from 0.49 to 0.56, indicating moderate effect sizes. These results suggest that gradiometers are more sensitive to ASD-related neural processing abnormalities. Conversely, the magnetometer channels showed fewer significant channels in Tier 1 and 2 which indicates that the magnetometers might be less sensitive to the localized neural activity relating to auditory-processing impairment in ASD.

Each tier was chosen with sample channels that were used as examples to reflect the statistically significant differences that were observed between the typically developing (TD) and autism spectrum disorder (ASD) groups. Sample graphs were created accordingly to give a graphical representation of the data.

Figure 1: MEG0133 (Tier 1, Strong Significant) indicates that there is a clear difference in variance between the TD and ASD groups. The boxplot and the violation plot show that the two groups have significant differences, which is depicted by the p-value of 0.018, hence depicting a significant statistical difference. The Means ± SEM plot indicates that the ASD group has a far greater variance than TD group with an ANOVA F value of 5.9 and a p-value of 0.018. Cohen’s d value of -0.558 is indicative of a moderate effect size, as indicated by the effect size plot. This suggests that MEG0133 is a significant channel for the differentiation of the TD and ASD groups.

Figure 1: Sample channel **MEG0133** (Tier 1, Strong)

Figure 2: MEG0111 (Tier 2, Moderate Significance), which shows the difference in the variance between the typical developing (TD) and autism spectrum disorder (ASD) groups. The boxplot and the violin plot show a moderate difference in distribution as the p -value is 0.056 and the Cohen d is 0.466, so it represents a moderate effect size. The Means ± SEM plot corroborates this, with an ANOVA F-value of 3.8 and a p-value of 0.056, indicating moderate significance among the groups.

Figure 2: Sample channel **MEG0111** (Tier 2, Moderate)

Figure 3: Channel MEG0222 (Tier 3, Weak Significance) shows that the difference between the variance between the TD and ASD groups is lower. Despite the fact that the boxplot and violin plot imply the existence of some separation, the p-value at 0.109 shows that the difference between the two is not statistically meaningful. The Means \pm SEM plot indicates that there is more variance in the ASD group compared to the TD group but the results of the ANOVA with F of 2.6 and P value of 0.109 indicate that the difference is not significant. According to the effect-size plot the effect-size is Cohen d = -0.373 which is low to moderate. Consequently, MEG0222 is not a robust channel for distinguishing between the TD and ASD groups.

Figure 3: Sample channel **MEG0222** (Tier 3, Weak)

Figure 4: MEG0332 (Tier 4, Non-Significant) reveals negligible variance difference between the TD and ASD groups. The Boxplot and Violin Plot illustrate overlapping distributions, with a p-value of 0.824, indicating no statistically significant difference between the groups. The Means \pm SEM figure further corroborates this by demonstrating that both groups possess equivalent mean variance values (ANOVA $F = 0.1$, p-value = 0.824). The effect Size plot indicates Cohen's d = -0.052, signifying a negligible influence. The results indicate that MEG0332 is not significant in distinguishing between the TD and ASD groups.

Figure 4: Sample channel MEG0332 (Tier 3, Non-significant)

This study used a sensor-level MEG analysis to find significant channels that were linked to differences in how the TD and ASD groups processed sound. In the statistical analysis that we conducted, we utilized independent t-tests and Cohen's d to determine the effect size. During our investigation, we discovered that a number of channels displayed significant differences between the two groups. Gradiometer channels are significantly stronger when compared to magnetometer channels and with more prominent channels detected in Tier 1 (Strong Significant) and Tier 2 (Moderate Significant). The Cohen's d values of gradiometers (ranged from 0.49 to 0.56) represent moderate effect sizes. Magnetometer channels were less significant with fewer in Tier 1 and Tier 2, indicating that they are less sensitive to auditory processing deficits associated with ASD.

Despite the fact that our investigations are beneficial in comprehending the critical channels of differentiation between TD and ASD groups, this study is constrained by numerous limitations. Sensor-specific limitations: The sensitivity of gradiometers was higher than that of magnetometers, which may be attributed to the characteristics of the sensor types. Future studies should may address the potential for integrating both types of sensors to enhance the sensitivity of the analysis. Although the current study centered on single channels, source localization in the context of multiple channels can potentially add to our understanding of brain operations. Scaling the analysis up to the source level might show larger patterns and regions of the brain that are engaged.

Future studies should extend this analysis to multiple channels and perform source localization to capture the broader neural networks involved in auditory processing in ASD. This would lead to a more comprehensive picture of spatial and temporal activity in the brain. Combining gradiometer and magnetometer data using machine learning models could enhance the predictive power of the analysis. Additionally, integrating neuroimaging techniques such as fMRI could offer a more detailed view of the brain regions involved in auditory processing and ASD.

Conclusion

This paper creates sensor level MEG data on auditory processing biomarkers for young children. Gradiometer channels are found to have comparatively better sensitivity to ADS related abnormal auditory processing with significant channel Tier 1 (significance) which confirms their improved spatial specificity to cortical auditory processing. The tier classification that we have (strong/moderate/weak/non) would enable us to select further studies to saleable channels. More adjustments were necessary in future research to enhance the sensitivity of magnetometer channels and to consider using machine learning in conjunction with neuroimaging technologies to achieve more detailed findings.

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